

Applying user participation to provide insight into the needs of interactive local food maps in Berkshire, Hampshire and Oxfordshire

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Summary

Over the last decade, visualisation research in cartography has frequently used design approaches, specifically geo-visualisation usability, but there is still a gap in how user-oriented approaches can be adapted to cartography effectively. Despite this gap, many exemplary usability studies have become a part of practice-based studies in cartography. This paper focuses on user research based on users' needs, conducting surveys with locals in three counties – Berkshire, Hampshire and Oxfordshire – in the UK. The surveys put forward the requirements of a local food map in a user-oriented way to design an optimal map for finding locally produced food.

KEYWORDS: Local food map, User research, User-centred design

1. Applying user participation to provide insight into the needs of interactive local food maps in the UK

The relationship between locals and their sourcing of locally produced food in a spatially local area is worth examining because of the possible effects on eating habits and healthy lifestyles. Interdisciplinary practice-based studies demonstrate that drawing people's attention to their surrounding environment can be promoted with novel interface design approaches (Dixon, 2018). This research investigates how design can help people locate locally produced food on a local food map. Here, a user-centred approach plays a crucial role in understanding user needs, and information design becomes an efficient approach for data visualisation by contributing to the investigation of representation. As an initial stage of making a local food map, this paper explores the meaning of local food and the interest of locals in local food, considering the overlapping principles of user-centred design and community-based participatory design that are exploited to investigate how to make the information applicable to users.

Design methods can be applied to novel visualisation studies involving users or experts (Moere et al., 2011). Recent research also indicates the necessity of reimagining map readers as map users with digital interactivity (Roth et al., 2017). Further, scholars of cartography recommend that user participation should form part of the entire design process, including 'work domain analysis, conceptual development, prototyping, interaction/usability assessment, implementation and debugging' (Robinson et al., 2005). Hence, this paper draws attention to locals' participation as the preliminary stage of making an optimal local food map, by focusing on users' needs regarding locally produced food in three counties – Berkshire, Hampshire and Oxfordshire – in the UK.

1.1. Redefining 'local food' for the local food map

The needs of locals who are keen on local food should first be broadly considered to obtain a practical definition of 'local food'. Even though the local system is defined as the opposite of the global system in general, many consumers believe that it would be possible to grow local food regionally

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(Ostrom, 2013; Meyerding et al., 2019). Besides, the term ‘local’ might be framed as a 100-mile radius or a location accessible by foot or bicycle (Ostrom, 2013). For most ‘locavores’, who prefer to eat only locally grown foods, food must be within a 100–200-mile radius (Green and Phillips, 2013). These concerns surrounding scale awareness reduce environmental footprint and frame the meaning of ‘local’ spatially.

The term ‘local food’ also indicates a geographic restriction based on the parameters of the word ‘local’. Furthermore, rural areas in the UK also stand out regarding geographical proximity to local food retail places when considering distance and food miles. The Local Authority Districts Level Classification measures rurality in the UK and classifies areas as ‘Significant Rural’, ‘Rural 50’ and ‘Rural 80’ (The Rural Evidence Research Centre, Birkbeck College, University of London, 2005). Hence, Berkshire, Hampshire and Oxfordshire, which include different levels of rural districts, were included in this research to gain insight into the relationship between local food and locals in geographically different areas.

1.2. Collecting users’ needs at farmers’ markets

User-centred design investigates user needs and involves the users in specific stages of the design cycle (Abrams and Maloney-Krichmar, 2014). My study also takes a user-centred approach to understand locals’ needs for local food maps, with a focus on user participation as a central part of the development process in the design cycle. At the same time, UK farmers’ markets (FMs), as the most common form of local food system, have come to prominence as an efficient way of obtaining local food and collaborating with locals. Thus, the user research has determined the requirements for local food maps with a survey conducted at 11 farmers’ markets in Berkshire, Hampshire and Oxfordshire between 1 June 2019 and 7 July 2019.

The survey was conducted with 53 consumers and 25 vendors at Windsor, Guildford, Banbury, Hampshire, Reading, Caversham, East Oxford, Newbury, Deddington, Vale Harvest and Gloucester FMs. The survey gathered responses to gain insights into why consumers buy from FMs and how vendors sell their products. Both participant groups were also asked about their online selling/buying habits regarding local food.

The survey showed that consumer visits to farmers’ markets are strongly influenced by several factors, the most important appearing to be the quality and range of products and accessibility of the markets. Prices, car parking and ease of access to other outlets are the secondary reasons given. Consumers who had purchased local food were also asked a set of rating scale questions to provide reasoning for their decision. Consumer motivations indicated some specific points, such as the high quality of products, supporting local business, knowing more about what they are eating, buying local food, and healthy eating/lifestyle, as listed in **Table 1**.

In addition, both groups were asked about their online habits. Thirty-six consumers shopped online. Convenience dominated as the main reason; the secondary reason given was ‘Easier to see products’. The 17 consumers who did not shop online indicated ‘I would like to see what I would buy’ as a primary reason for not shopping online. However, 19 consumers bought food online and 3 of them indicated they bought local food online. These 19 consumers used social media/websites to find out about local food. The final question aimed to discover whether consumers would be interested in a new map system to find local food. Thirty-nine consumers indicated that if there were a new online system to learn about local food, they would be interested in it. The primary reasons for interest were that consumers would like to gather information about local food and know more about where food comes from through one channel. Supporting local business and staying local dominated the second reasons given.

Table 1
Importance of reasons given in the survey for shopping at farmers' markets by number of people

Importance of the following features	Very	Some	Not
The high quality of products	50	3	
Supporting local business	50	3	
Knowing more about what you are eating	47	3	3
Buying local food	47	5	1
Healthy eating/lifestyle	41	12	1
Ease of access	36	10	7
Shared values between consumers and vendors	31	18	4
Spending time with others who engage with local community	30	13	10
Reasonable prices	21	29	2
Ease of car parking	19	12	22

The survey showed that most of the vendors ascribed their cooperation with the FMs to locality or money. Twenty vendors had a website, and of those, nineteen said that their web sites efficiently represented their products. Only seven vendors said they sold online. Of those, five sold via email addresses and two via social media accounts. Others who did not sell online mentioned their reasons for not doing so as being old or alone, delivery cost, packaging/delivering, time, and convenience. These points highlight business capacity as well as online habits.

Results indicate the primary motivations of consumers for visiting FMs are freshness, taste, quality, and localness. Further, conversations at FMs highlighted the importance of community involvement. This investigation showed that an interactive map might meet users' needs for finding locally produced food by including social communication opportunities and detailed product information. Hence, my broader research will focus on design scenarios considering locals' concerns as the next step. The survey outcomes that need to be visualised will be interpreted, fixed with scenarios, and classified depending on the data type to be represented before the visualisation process.

2. References

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4. Biography

Esra Bulut Peynirci is a PhD researcher in Typography & Graphic Communication at the University of Reading. Specialising in user-centred design, her main research interest is promoting better communication methods between map designers and map users in a user-oriented way.